

Laboratory study of the hydrological response of Green Roofs with Expanded Clay and Crumb Rubber under extreme rainfall events

V. Andrés-Valeri^{1,*}, A. Lemos-Galindez¹, I. Lombillo², S. García-Argüelles¹, A. Roldan-Valcarce¹ & J. Rodriguez-Hernandez¹

¹GITECO Research Group, ETSICCP, Universidad de Cantabria, Av. Los Castros 44, 39005, Santander, Cantabria, Spain

²GTED Research Group, ETSICCP, Universidad de Cantabria, Av. Los Castros 44, 39005, Santander, Cantabria, Spain

*Corresponding author email: andresv@unican.es

Highlights

- Extreme rainfall simulations were applied over three Green Roofs models with alternative materials.
- Expanded Clay and Crumb Rubber showed to be suitable drainage layer materials for Green Roofs
- Expanded Clay Aggregates showed higher water retention capacities than Crumb Rubber.

Introduction

Mitigation of urban flooding has become an issue of concern in most cities in the world due to the several problems related to extreme rainfall events in urban areas, including economical losses, environmental impacts and amenity disturbance for citizens (Castro-Fresno et al., 2013). In this context, Green Roofs (GR) arise as one of the most common and well-known Nature Based Solution (NbS) for sustainable stormwater management in urban areas. GR are normally composed by a set of 4 different layers over the waterproofing and root protection layer: drainage layer, filtering layer, substrate, and vegetation (Czemiel Berndtsson, 2010). GR have been found to retain close to 60% of rainfall volumes on average in a variety of climates, and to reduce between 27% and 86% of the yearly stormwater runoff (Czemiel Berndtsson, 2010; Stovin et al., 2012). When totally saturated, the hydraulic performance of GR tends to be similar to standard roofs, so their capacity to improve stormwater management is directly related to their water retention capacity. Stormwater retention capacity showed to relate to various factors. Rainfall events with higher rainfall volumes lead to a lower runoff reduction (Carter & Rasmussen, 2006). Something similar occurs with rainfall intensity, as lower intensities lead to higher retention capacities (Czemiel Berndtsson, 2010). Antecedent dry period is also an influential factor as water evaporation reduces water content in GR, allowing a higher water storage capacity (Stovin et al., 2012). Some studies also reported the influence of GR in delaying the runoff peaks in relation to conventional roofs and lowering the peak outflow intensity. GR design and the used materials showed to be influential factors in water retention capacity. Especially important are the type of vegetation used, the substrate thickness and its characteristics, and the drainage layer design and its composition (Kazemi et al., 2023). In this research, two different materials were assessed as drainage layer in GR structures: Expanded Clay Aggregates (ECA) and Crumb Rubber Aggregates (CRA). With these materials, three GR laboratory models were constructed and rainfall simulations were applied over the models in order to assess their runoff retention capacity.

Methodology

Materials Used

Three different GR models of 0.6m length and 0.3m width were built for this laboratory study, each of them with a different material as drainage layer: CRA and two different gradations of ECA, as showed in Table 1.

Table 1. Drainage layer characteristics for each laboratory model

Model	Abbreviation	Drainage Layer	Gradation	Density
Green Roof Model 1	CRA	Crumb Rubber Aggregates	2-4mm	330 Kg/m ³
Green Roof Model 2	ECA1	Expanded Clay Aggregates	10-20 mm	283 Kg/m ³
Green Roof Model 3	ECA2	Expanded Clay Aggregates	2-10 mm	283 Kg/m ³

The models were waterproofed with a transparent PVC membrane and thermally insulated at the bottom and lateral sides, and a geotextile for protection was placed over the waterproof membrane. The drainage

layer was placed over the geotextile with a fixed thickness of 0.10 m after a simple rodded compaction. Another geotextile was placed over the drainage layer to prevent the migration of substrate particles. Geotextile used was a 1.9 mm thick non-woven polyester one with a specific weight of 150 g/m², permeability of 0.044 m/s and a characteristic opening size of 90µm. Over the separation geotextile, a 0.12 m layer of a commercial substrate with a density of 1060 Kg/m³ and a content of organic matter of 29% was placed. Two different vegetal species, selected according to the bibliography and their local availability, were planted in the substrate: *Sedum Album* and *Sedum Reflexum*. Construction of laboratory models is showed in Figure 1a, and a scheme of the cross section of each laboratory model is showed in Figure 1b.

Figure 1. (a) Construction process of laboratory models and (b) scheme of the cross section of laboratory models

Methods

The laboratory models were tested to assess their response to extreme rainfall events. Rainfall was simulated by using 15 droppers over each laboratory model and controlling the flow by a flowmeter. The laboratory models were placed with a fixed slope of 5% and the outflow water from each model was collected in a chamber and measured with 2 minutes interval during 20 minutes, with a final measurement after 120 minutes to obtain the Retained Rainfall (RR) after this period. The time passed since the beginning of rainfall simulation and the beginning of the outflow, named Lag Time (LT), was also measured. Rainfall volume was fixed at 60mm/h as it is the maximum 24 hours rainfall height in the last 30 years in the city of Santander (Spain). Two different extreme rainfall intensities were simulated to assess the influence of this parameter in the performance of the GR models: 300 mm/h and 600 mm/h. As the simulated rainfall volume is the same for all tests, the rainfall duration was 12 minutes and 6 minutes for each intensity, respectively. Finally, in order to assess the influence of the antecedent dry period, rainfall simulations were performed in two different scenarios: with the laboratory models totally saturated after a simulated rainfall of 60 mm and 24 hours of air drying (first scenario), and after a drying time of 7 days prior to testing (second scenario). To reproduce the environmental conditions of the on-site applications, a day-night cycle (12hours each) was simulated during the whole experimentation by using three OSRAM Ultra Vitalux 300W bulbs, placed at 50 cm over the vegetation (one bulb over each model), in order to reproduce the average solar radiation in the city of Santander and to allow the vegetation survival during the whole experimentation. The room temperature, surface temperature and drainage layers' temperatures were also measured by temperature probes placed over the lamps, in the substrate and under the drainage layers, respectively. The experimental setup can be seen in Figure 2a and the average hourly temperature along the day is showed in Figure 2b.

Results and discussion

Figures 3 and 4 show the obtained results for the rainfall simulations over the three laboratory models for the two tested rainfall intensities and the two analysed scenarios. The results showed that the studied GF models have different hydrological responses to rainfall depending on the drainage layer composition and

characteristics. In saturated conditions, LT showed to be in the range of 53 seconds and 150 seconds for a rainfall intensity of 300 mm/h, and between 40 seconds and 90 seconds for a rainfall intensity of 600 mm/h, being higher for GR models with ECA drainage layers.

Figure 2. (a) Experimental set-up during rainfall simulations and (b) Averaged hourly temperature for the whole experimentation

Something similar occurs with the RR after 120 minutes, that showed to be between 3.72mm and 7.51mm for the rainfall intensity of 300 mm/h and between 3.76mm and 6.94mm for the intensity of 600 mm/h, being higher for ECA drainage layers. The finer gradation (ECA2) showed the higher LT and RR values for both rainfall intensities, practically doubling the values of the coarser gradation (ECA1).

Figure 3. Rainfall simulations results for the first scenario (saturated models): (a) CRA, 300mm/h, 12 min. (b) ECA1, 300mm/h, 12 min. (c) ECA2, 300mm/h, 12 min. (d) CRA, 600mm/h, 6 min. (e) ECA1, 600mm/h, 6 min. (f) ECA2, 600mm/h, 6 min.

In the second scenario, with a previous dry period of 1 week, the results showed higher LT and RR for all the tested models in comparison with the first scenario, indicating the significant influence of the antecedent dry period in the runoff attenuation and mitigation capacity of GR. With all, results of the second scenario showed similar patterns than those observed in the first scenario, so that higher intensities lead to slightly lower LT and RR volumes. It was observed that LT ranged from 59 to 157 seconds for an intensity of 300 mm/h and between 44 and 99 seconds for intensities of 600mm/h, being in all cases higher in models with ECA drainage layers. A similar performance takes place with RR, that showed to be in the range of 4.66-11.66mm for the intensity of 300mm/h and between 3.97 and 9.15mm for 600mm/h. Results of both scenarios and for the two tested rainfall intensities showed a better performance of the GR models with ECA aggregates as drainage layer, especially ECA2 (2-10mm), which provide a water retention capacity up to 11.66 mm after 120 minutes and LT up to 157 seconds.

Figure 4. Rainfall simulations results for the second scenario (unsaturated models): (a) CRA, 300mm/h, 12 min. (b) ECA1, 300mm/h, 12 min. (c) ECA2, 300mm/h, 12 min. (d) CRA, 600mm/h, 6 min. (e) ECA1, 600mm/h, 6 min. (f) ECA2, 600mm/h, 6 min.

Conclusions and future work

- Rainfall intensity showed to be more influential on the LT variation, while antecedent dry period was more influential in RR. Doubling rainfall intensity, from 300 to 600mm/h, reduces the LT around 30% for all the tested materials, while increasing antecedent dry period 1 week increases RR up to 55%.
- ECA outperformed CRA in terms of runoff retention and mitigation, increasing LT up to 183% for 300mm/h intensity and saturated conditions, while RR is increased up to 150% for 300mm/h intensity and 1 week of antecedent dry period.
- Gradation of the used drainage layer also influences runoff retention and mitigation, being higher for finer gradations. ECA2 (2-10mm) outperformed ECA1 (10-20mm), reaching maximum values of RR of 11.66mm and LT of 157 seconds after a dry period of 1 week.
- Future research includes assessing the performance of the tested GR models with rainfall simulations fitted to real hydrological data and validate the obtained results with on-site applications.

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